

Immunofluorescence on 2D enteroids to assess the cell composition

Note1: for the reagents refer to “List of reagents for enteroid protocols” (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13847508)

Note2: Refer to protocol “Generation of 2D enteroid culture” (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13849461)

Note3: this protocol is performed on 8 well chamber slide. Primary antibody used in this protocol: anti-Sox9, Anti-villin, anti-Lyz, anti-CgA, anti-Muc2.

- 1) Remove the media from the enteroid monolayer in 48 well plate and add 300 μ L 4% paraformaldehyde/PBS for 15' at room temperature
- 2) Remove the fixative and wash 2 times with PBSL
- 3) Incubate in 2D Permeabilization Buffer for 10' at room temperature (RT)
- 4) Wash twice with 2D Washing Buffer (WB)
- 5) Incubate in 2D Blocking Buffer for 30' at RT
- 6) Remove Blocking Buffer and incubate with primary antibody in 2D diluent buffer at the appropriate dilution, overnight at 4°C
- 7) Wash 3 times for 5' with WB on a rocking platform
- 8) Incubate with secondary antibody diluted in AB diluent buffer for 1,5h a RT
- 9) Stain cell nuclei with DAPI in PBSL for 15' at RT
- 10) Wash 3 times for 5' with WB on a rocking platform
- 11) Mount the slide with a coverslip and the mounting medium